

Nantucket Biodiversity Initiative 2014 – Final Report

Using Ground-Penetrating Radar to Map Buried Trunks of Prostrate-Growing Eastern Red Cedar Trees on Coskata/Coatue Wildlife Refuge.

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Abstract:

We used Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR) transects, which is not disruptive to trees and substrate, to test whether it could be used to provide evidence of underground stems and roots of low-growing Eastern Red Cedars on the Coataue/Coskata Wildlife Refuge, Nantucket. This coastal Maritime Juniper Woodland/Shrubland, is classified as a critically imperiled natural community. These trees described as dwarf cedars, are better described as large, prostrate-growing trees buried by sand with exposed, upright-growing branches in this dynamic, coastal habitat. GPR signals using 200 MHz antennas were collected to create profile images showing diffractions in the sand substrate. Interpretations of several profile images showed diffractions that are likely from trunks, branches or roots. Above ground tree dimensions were measured with one tree 16 m long x 6 m wide and only 1.75 m tall. Exposed roots were observed growing north-northwest, toward shore, and above ground portions growing south-southeast, away from prevailing winds. Core samples of some branches were taken to determine ages of branches, and whether it was stem or root material, which differs morphologically. Ring counts from core samples taken on exposed trunks of the larger trees indicate ages of 55+ years, with severe stress signals in the rings.

Introduction

Coskata/Coataue Wildlife Refuge has the largest coastal Eastern Red Cedar (ERC) woodland in New England (TTOR. 2014). It is classified by Massachusetts Natural Heritage and Endangered Species Program (NHESP) as Maritime Juniper Woodland/Shrublands with a state rank S1 (critically imperiled) in Massachusetts (NHESP. 2010). The Nature Conservancy has classified this community as Maritime Red-cedar Woodland (TNC. 2000). Eastern Red Cedars (*Juniperus virginiana*) growing here live in a dynamic maritime environment exposed to strong north-northwest winds and salt spray from Nantucket Sound. The barrier beaches and vegetation along Coataue protect Nantucket Harbor and the main island (Fig. 1).

Although these low-growing ERC's are described as dwarf cedars (NCF 2014) we hypothesized that many of these smaller plants are really larger trees that have been growing prostrate and were buried by sand over time leaving exposed, upright-growing branches. These trees are growing horizontally in a

south-southeast direction away from prevailing wind.

During a Nantucket Biodiversity Initiative survey in 2012 to describe the vegetation community at Wyer's Point Biodiversity Plot on Coatue, individual clumps of ERC were measured for height, diameter and length and the distance between separate clumps. Plants found closer to the foredune along Nantucket Sound had the lowest height. Along a north-northwest to south-southeast transect there is a gradual increase in height from low-growing plants to taller, upright trees towards the harbor or inland side of Coatue. Trunks and branches appeared to have been buried and exposed by sand. Above ground branches grow upright and can cover a large area with some measured 10.0 m long by 10.0 m wide but less than 1.5 m tall (Polloni & Lombardi. 2012). Gaps in above ground growth are thought to be connected by buried trunks and branches. Both trunks and roots exhibit twisted gnarly growth habits and it can be difficult to visually distinguish trunks from exposed roots.

Frequently clumps were observed to have the same color variation between plants even 3-5 meters apart which may indicate they are connected and the same plant. Another observation during the 2012 survey was of an exposed stem along a sand track road that connected 2 clumps, one on each side of the road, approximately 3 meters apart with upright branches showing the similar color.

“Coatue beach is still bordered by a line of ancient cedars...One such tree which was killed by the salt spray in 1933 showed 107 years of wood rings. Its top had a spread of 24 feet and it was only 5 feet tall.” (Rice. 1933). With this information these trees could be quite old and large. (Fig. 2)

We tested whether Ground-penetrating Radar (GPR) could provide information about whether clumps of upright growing branches are connected by buried tree trunks rather than separate, dwarf-shrubs or trees. GPR has been used successfully to detect and map tree roots, and determine root biomass in sandy soils (Bassuk. 2011). This is a non-invasive method that can be used to determine whether clumps separated by 1-5 m are actually connected by buried trunks. The normal growth habit of ERC is upright (unlike the related Pasture Juniper (*Juniperus communis*) which naturally grows low to the ground).

The purpose of this study is to understand the growth habit of these trees. This information can be

useful for conservation management decisions such as best locations for sand track roads to avoid destruction of these ancient trees by vehicular traffic and other potential threats. In addition it can contribute to understanding the impacts of rising sea level and climate change in this dynamic maritime habitat.

In addition core samples taken from prostrate trees and roots were taken by Jessie Pearl, dendrochronologist, to observe the difference between stem wood and root wood since it is difficult by visual observation to determine whether we were looking at trunk or roots because of gnarly growth habit.

Methods

We collected the GPR data with a Ramac Ground Penetrating Radar unit with 100 to 200 MHz antennas (Fig. 3). The images are displayed as “GPR sections” or profiles. Transect locations were selected based on whether two separated clumps appeared similar, where roots were exposed some distance from above ground branches, or near trunks to look for buried roots or stems.

A GPR trace was collected every 0.25, 0.10, or 0.05 m using 200 MHz antennas along each transect with GPR data organized by file number (C1, C2, ...) and line number (1, 2, 3, ...). These antennas successfully penetrated to as much as 10 meters depth.

Buried tree roots and stems should return GPR energy, but the roots and stems are relatively small features compared to the wavelengths of the 200 MHz GPR. We used the following processing steps to enhance the GPR signal. First, we removed low frequency noise using a signal saturation correction filter. Next, we bandpass filtered between 20 to 250 MHz followed by removal of the average trace of the traces. This step removed the strong air wave and ground wave arrivals from the data. Finally, we applied an automatic gain to the data to enhance weaker later arriving energy. To convert the time axis to a depth axis, we used a velocity of 0.10 m/ns based on diffracted arrivals in the various data sections.

A GIS generated map using QGIS map application and gps recorded coordinates of each file location (C1, C2, ...) using a Garmin GPSmap 60CSx unit in the field. A map was created using 2014 zone 20

USGS Color Ortho Imagery from MASS GIS. Several lines were often done along the same transect but at different increments and were given a different line number but would have the same file number.

Individual trees were then measured for length, width, and height along the southeast-northwest axis on which they were growing. Notes were recorded such as gap between trees thought to be connected, or distance of exposed stem from line. Several trees along a line are identified as T1, T2... or if they were thought to be connected and the line went between a gap in above ground branches, they were identified as T1A, T1B...

Cores from prostrate trees and roots were taken to observe the difference between stem wood and root wood. Trees were cored using an increment borer following standard dendrochronology procedures (Fritts, 1972; Stolkes 1968). All cores were glued to wooden mounts and sanded to 400 grit to observe cellular structure and annual rings under a microscope by Jessie Pearl, contributing dendrochronologist (Fig. 4).

Results

A total of 4 days was spent in the field in Coatie in May, 2015. Fifteen locations along transects of varying length were recorded as Files (C1, C2...) and 19 lines were recorded (Table 1.) and shown on GIS generated map (Fig. 5). Several repeats (Line) were done at a particular location (File) with different distance increments where antennas were placed along the transect line. Increments varied and were 0.25 m, 0.1 m, or 0.05 m. This was to ensure that the best results could be attained with variations and background noise encountered in the field.

Thirteen trees or sections of trees were measured (Table 2.). The largest trees measured along transects during this study were 9.3 m long x 9.2 m wide and 1.1 m tall. Almost all the trees measured were close to the same length and width giving them a somewhat round appearance with the direction of growth consistently from NW to SE. One tree that was selected for a core sample only was 16 m long by 6.5 m wide and 1.75 m tall. Most of the trees measured were less than 1m tall except one that was furthest back from the Nantucket Sound shore.

Several of the profiles showing object signals were subsequently processed further to remove trace signals that blurred the visual results.

Discussion

The tree roots and stems act like point diffractors in the subsurface, causing the reflected energy to have a characteristic hyperbolic shape. These hyperboles are easily seen in the presented GPR data. Before the average trace removal, the air and ground waves masked these events (Fig. 6).

We acquired line 17 along the access road (Figure 7.). The hyperbolic arrivals from the buried tree mass were much clearer after the average trace removal step. The hyperbolae originate a few 10s of centimeters below the surface. The hyperbolae are centered over the tree root or stem so we can determine their location as the apex of the curve. The apex indicates the depth and location of the buried feature along the profile but not the width of the tree root or stem (Fig. 8).

Line 18 is along the same transect as line 17, but with a trace spacing of 0.05 m and covers the distance between about 6.7 m and 9.7 m of line 17 (Figs. 9 & 10).

ERC tree roots and larger stems and trunks can be located using GPR with 200MHz antenna, however, to better image the buried tree roots and stems, we recommend using higher frequency GPR antennas, perhaps 400 MHz or higher. The trees are buried in clean sand, so penetration depth should not be an issue with the higher frequency antennas which may provide more highly resolved images of the roots and stems.

The longer wavelengths of the 200 MHz antennas blur the returns from the buried features. This can make it difficult to have clear images of small diameter tree branches and roots although in several images, larger roots were observed. It was realized that the clumps of trees had many small buried branches probably less than 5 cm diameter that were not resolved clearly with the equipment used. Lower frequencies can penetrate to greater depths but may have blurred results from smaller objects whereas higher frequencies penetrate to shallower depths but returns result in sharper hyperbola and clearer images of small diameter objects within a profile.

Late in the project during exploration of Coatue away from the study area, several exposed trees were found. They were growing horizontally and provided us with a good view of what is probably a typical growth pattern for these trees. The base of the trunk can be very distant from the above ground tree branches (Fig. 11).

Multiple stems or branches can make it difficult to get clear returns of radar signal if they are too narrow in diameter (Fig. 12).

Layering was not observed for either tree indicating roots did not form adventitiously along the stems.

What makes Eastern Red Cedar difficult for dendrochronology:

“Converging rings, fake rings, and bands of premature late wood in Eastern Red Cedars make it difficult to determine annual rings. Cross-dating the trees is, therefore, inherently complex. Rough ring counts for age were preformed. Rough ring counts of the samples produced cedar ages from 15-55 years, with the majority of the trees aging 25- 55 years old.

Key differences between root and trunk cells:

The pith (center of the tree: oldest ring) of the trunk of *Juniperus virginiana* is a star or triangle shape compared to the ‘pith’ of root wood, which is square (Fig. 13). The rings of the root wood are very small with thin latewood bands, and it was noticed that root wood had darker coloration than the corresponding trunk wood (Fig. 14)” (Pearl, 2015).

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Literature

- Bassuk, N., J. Grabosky, A. Mucciardi, & G. Raffel. 2011. *Ground-penetration radar locates tree roots in two soil media under pavement*. *Arboriculture & Urban Forestry* 37 (4): 160-166
- Fritts, Harold C. 1972. *Dendroclimatology and Dendroecology*. Seattle, WA: U. of Washington.
- NCF (Nantucket Conservation Foundation). 2014. Nantucket Conservation Foundation – Coatue, 2014. www.nantucketconservation.org/property/coatue/. (Site accessed 2014)
- NHESP (Natural Heritage and Endangered Species Program). 2010. Maritime Red Cedar Woodland/Shrubland. Factsheet. <http://www.mass.gov/eea/docs/dfg/nhesp/natural-communities-facts/maritime-juniper-woodland-shrubland-factsheet.pdf>
- NHESP Priority Types of Natural Communities. 2013. <http://www.mass.gov/eea/docs/dfg/nhesp/natural-communities-facts/priority-natural-commun.pdf>
- Polloni & Lombardi. 2012. Wyer's Point Biodiversity Plot Botanical Survey, Coatue, Nantucket. NBI Small Research Grant. Unpublished report.
- Stokes, M., and T. Smiley. 1968. *An Introduction to Tree-Ring Dating*, University of Chicago Press, Chicago, IL
- TNC (The Nature Conservancy). 2000. National Vegetation Classification – Eastern United States, Ecoregion 62 subset. Draft. 2000.
- TTOR (The Trustees of Reservations). 2014. <http://www.thetrustees.org/places-to-visit/cape-cod-islands/coskata-coatue.html> (accessed 2014).

Figure 1. Coatue study location

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Figure 2. Horizontal tree with exposed trunk in sand road

Figure 3. Collecting GPR signals

Figure 4. Jessie Pearl taking core sample to determine trunk and root ring differences

Figure 5. Map of Line numbers

Figure 6. GPR profile image

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Figure 7. GPR raw profile 17 image.

Figure 8. Profile 17 post-process.

Figure 9. GPR raw profile 18 image.

Figure 10. Profile 18 post-process.

Figure 11. Exposed tree.

Figure 12. Exposed tree (still living) with many narrow branches/trunks. Approximately 6 m long.

Figure 13. Trunk core showing star shaped pith

Figure 14. Showing detail of root wood.

Table 1.							
File Name	Line no.	Step size (m)	GPS WP #	Lat	Long	Date	notes
C1	1	0.25	139	41.335071	-70.034059	05/12/15	
C1	2	0.25	139	41.335071	-70.034059	05/12/15	
C2	3	0.25				05/12/15	
C3	4	0.1				05/12/15	
C2	5	0.1				05/12/15	repeat of line 3
C1	6	0.1	139	41.335071	-70.034059	05/12/15	
C4	7	0.1	140	41.334495	-70.034018	05/12/15	
C5	8	0.1	141	41.334412	-70.033939	05/12/15	
C6	9	0.1	141			05/12/15	perpendicular line
C7	10	0.1	142	41.333871	-70.034716	05/13/15	
C8	11	0.1	142	41.333871	-70.034716	05/13/15	repeat of line 10
C8	12	0.1	142	41.333871	-70.034716	05/13/15	repeat of line 10
C9	13	0.1	143	41.333731	-70.034816	05/13/15	
C10	14	0.1	143	41.333731	-70.034816	05/13/15	
C11	15	0.1	144	41.33353	-70.034793	05/13/15	
C12	16	0.1	145	41.333403	-70.034894	05/13/15	
C13	17	0.1	146	41.336195	-70.033338	05/13/15	
C13	18	0.05	146	41.336195	-70.033338	05/13/15	
C14	19	0.05	149	41.342381	-70.029844	05/13/15	
C15	19	0.05	149	41.342381	-70.029844	05/13/15	
core sample			151	41.345818	-70.028362	05/14/15	

Table 2.							
tree id	File #	length	width	height	notes	Line #	
T1	C1	4.40	3.90	0.80		1,2,6	
T2	C1	8.70	7.00	1.60	exposed stem 1.3m from line	1,2,6	
T3	C1	9.30	9.20	1.10		1,2,6	
T4	C1	7.60	7.20	0.75	exposed stem .5m from line	1,2,6	
T1	C4	1.25	1.30	0.49	1.15m gap between T1 and T2	7	
T1A	C4	1.20	1.30	0.54	1.15m gap between T1 and T2	7	
T1	C5	6.50	6.75	1.80	Pam's tree	8	
T1B	C7	6.50	6.30	0.80	this may be continous trees 17.8m long	10	
T1	C9	8.00	3.90	0.70	3.2m to beginning of exposed trunk	13	
T1	C11	5.30	5.20	0.80		15	
T1A	C12	3.2	2.70	0.40	gap between T1A and T1B is .75m	16	
T1B	C12	4.00	4.00	0.45	gap between T1A and T1B is .75m	16	
T1	C13, C14	6.80	6.30	0.75	was growing across road and stem? Or root was exposed	18,19	
T1	WP151	16.20	6.50	1.75	Core sample by Jessie Pearl. No profile done here.		